

EFFECTIVENESS OF DRIP IRRIGATION METHOD FOR COTTON IN SALINE SOILS

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Annotation This article presents the results of scientific research aimed at developing an irrigation regime for cultivating the Bukhara-102 cotton variety under the conditions of light loamy soils with salinity in the Bukhara region. The study focuses on identifying optimal elements of drip irrigation technology for these conditions. The efficiency of drip irrigation techniques in watering the Bukhara-102 cotton variety has been examined.

Key words: saline soils, drip irrigation, irrigation salt, dripper water consumption, distance between emitters, cotton yield.

As a result of global climate change, the glacier area in Central Asia has decreased by approximately 30% over the past 50-60 years. According to estimates, if the temperature rises by 2°C, the volume of glaciers will decrease by 50%, and if it increases by 4°C, the reduction could reach 78%. Calculations suggest that by 2050, water resources in the Syr Darya basin may decrease by 5%, while in the Amu Darya basin, the reduction could reach up to 15%. In Uzbekistan, the total water deficit exceeded 3 billion cubic meters by 2015. This shortage is expected to reach 7 billion cubic meters by 2030 and 15 billion cubic meters by 2050. In today's world, where global climate change and water scarcity are intensifying, the widespread adoption of water-saving irrigation technologies is crucial to mitigating the negative impacts of water shortages and ensuring stable and high-quality agricultural yields.

Scientists around the world are conducting research on priority areas to mitigate the negative consequences of global water scarcity. These efforts focus on the widespread implementation of water-saving technologies, improving the reclamation condition of saline soils, and ensuring high and stable agricultural yields.

In conditions of water scarcity, increasing the efficiency of water-saving irrigation technologies, achieving high and sustainable crop yields, improving the reclamation state of saline soils, optimizing the soil's water-physical properties and salt regime, and enhancing soil fertility have become promising directions for agricultural development.

Research Objective: The objective of the study is to determine the optimal irrigation technique elements for drip irrigation of the Bukhara-102 cotton variety under moderately saline, light loamy soils of Bukhara region. The study evaluates their impact on cotton growth, development, yield, and fiber quality indicators, as well as assesses the effect of drip irrigation on the reclamation regime of irrigated lands.

Research Object: The research focuses on meadow-alluvial, moderately saline, light loamy soils and the optimal irrigation technique elements for drip irrigation of the Bukhara-102 cotton variety.

Research Methods: The first field experiment was conducted from 2021 to 2023 in the “Niyoz Niyozov” farm, located in Samonchiq MFY, Jondor district, Bukhara region. The study was carried out on moderately saline, light loamy soils. The groundwater table in the experimental field was found at a depth of 1.8–2.4 meters, with mineralization levels ranging from 3.2 to 3.8 g/l.

To achieve the research objectives, field experiments were conducted using a unified system to determine the irrigation schedule and study the irrigation technique elements for drip irrigation of the Bukhara-102 cotton variety. The scientific research was carried out according to the methodology of “Field Experiment Methods” (PSUEAITI, 2007) in the V-hydromodule zone of Jondor district, Bukhara region, under light loamy soil conditions.

The experiment was conducted with 7 variants in 3 replications, arranged in a single tier. Each replication had an area of 720 m² (100 m in length and 7.2 m in width), resulting in a total experimental field area of 2160 m², while the overall field covered 15,120 m².

In all drip-irrigated variants of the field experiments, pre-irrigation soil moisture was maintained at 75-80-65% of the field capacity (FC), with uniform fertilizer application rates of N-200, P-150, K-100 kg/ha.

Additionally, in the furrow-irrigated control variant (Variant 1), irrigation was carried out at pre-irrigation soil moisture levels of 70-75-65% of FC, with fertilizer application rates of N-250, P-175, K-100 kg/ha.

Analysis and Results: Considering the urgent problems mentioned above, experiments on drip irrigation of cotton were conducted from 2021 to 2023 in the historically irrigated meadow-alluvial, light loamy, and moderately saline soils of the Bukhara region. In the control variant (Variant 1), traditional furrow irrigation was applied, while in Variants 2-7, the optimal irrigation technique elements were studied using the drip irrigation technology. In the drip irrigation method, dripper tapes were placed either in every furrow or alternately

between furrows. The water discharge rates of the drippers were as follows: 1.6 l/hour in Variants 2-3, 1.8 l/hour in Variants 4-5, 2.0 l/hour in Variants 6-7. The spacing between drippers was maintained at 40 cm in all drip irrigation variants. From 2021 to 2023, in the control variant (furrow irrigation, Variant 1), irrigation was carried out 6 times using the 1-4-1 system, with irrigation norms ranging from 786-1056 m³/ha, seasonal irrigation norms of 5212-5288 m³/ha, and a three-year average of 5246 m³/ha. The cotton yield in this variant was 38.3 centners/ha. In drip irrigation Variants 2-5, where the dripper discharge rates were 1.6 and 1.8 l/hour, with 40 cm spacing between drippers and 0.6 m spacing between dripper tapes, irrigation was applied 15-17 times using the 2-14-1 and 2-12-1 systems. The irrigation norms ranged from 215-321 m³/ha, and the seasonal irrigation norms were 3542-3714 m³/ha, with a cotton yield of 43.8-46.8 centners/ha. In Variant 6, where dripper discharge was 2.0 L/hour, with the same 40 cm dripper spacing and 0.6 m spacing between dripper pipes, irrigation was applied 14 times using the 2-11-1 system. The irrigation norms were 226-328 m³/ha, and the seasonal irrigation norm was 3389 m³/ha, achieving the highest cotton yield of 47.5 centners/ha.

Soil Salinity Analysis: To study the salt regime of the soil, samples were taken from 1-meter soil layers (0-30 cm, 30-70 cm, 70-100 cm) at the beginning and end of the growing season, as well as before and after each irrigation. The content of Cl, HCO₃, SO₄ ions and total dry residue was analyzed. At the beginning of the growing season, the Cl-ion concentration in the 0-30 cm layer was 0.008%, and in the 1-meter layer, it was 0.011%. The total dry residue in the 0-30 cm layer was 0.142%, and in the 1-meter layer, it was 0.226%. At the end of the season, in the control variant (furrow irrigation, Variant 1): The Cl-ion concentration in the 0-30 cm layer increased to 0.030%, and in the 1-meter layer, it was 0.034%. The total dry residue reached 0.234% in the 0-30 cm layer and 0.424% in the 1-meter layer. In Variant 6 (drip irrigation with 2.0 L/hour drippers placed in every furrow). The Cl-ion concentration in the 0-30 cm layer was 0.024%, and in the 1-meter layer, it was 0.027%. The total dry residue in the 0-30 cm layer was 0.175%, and in the 1-meter layer, it was 0.331%. Compared to the control variant, the Cl-ion accumulation was lower by 0.006-0.007%, and the total dry residue was lower by 0.059-0.093% in the drip irrigation variants. The lower accumulation of salts in the drip-irrigated soil can be attributed to the controlled water application that prevented excessive salt infiltration from irrigation water and minimized the upward movement of saline groundwater into the topsoil.

Conclusion: Based on the conducted research, it was determined that for drip irrigation of the Bukhara-102 cotton variety under moderately saline, meadow-alluvial, light loamy soils in the Bukhara region, the optimal irrigation technique elements include Dripper discharge rate: 2.0 l/hour, Dripper spacing: 40 cm Drip pipe spacing: 0.6 meters Using these parameters, pre-irrigation soil moisture was maintained at 75-80-65% of field capacity (FC), and irrigation was applied 14 times using the 2-11-1 system. The irrigation norms ranged from 226-328 m³/ha, with a seasonal irrigation norm of 3389 m³/ha, which resulted in saving 1857 m³/ha of water resources compared to the control variant. This approach allowed achieving a cotton yield of 47.5 centners/ha. Additionally, in the variant with a dripper discharge of 2.0 l/hour and a pipe spacing of 0.6 meters, the chlorine ion content in the soil was 0.024% in the 0-30 cm layer and 0.027% in the 1-meter layer. The total dry residue was 0.175% in the 0-30 cm layer and 0.331% in the 1-meter layer. Compared to the control variant, chlorine ion accumulation was 0.006-0.007% lower, and the total dry residue was 0.059-0.093% lower, indicating a reduction in soil salinity.

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